

Configurations of one-time calibrated FDDA for selected parameters verification

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Abstract—This work deals with different simulation configurations for verifying the function of a one-time digitally calibrated fully-differential difference amplifier (FDDA) designed in 130nm CMOS technology. In terms of calibration, the compensated parameter is in this case, the input offset voltage V_{IN_OFF} . Specific FDDA configurations based on open (OL) and closed (CL) feedback loops are presented here for simulation of parameters such as frequency and phase responses, V_{IN_OFF} , CMRR and PSRR parameters. Individual simulation configurations are divided into universal (pre-calibration) and post-calibration ones. In the case of CL, the effect of small-signal output resistance of the FDDA on its DC gain is analyzed through circuit model, which has to be considered in the low-voltage design.

Keywords—FDDA simulation, Open loop, Closed loop, Input offset voltage, Frequency response, Phase response, CMRR, PSRR, Low-voltage analog design, CMOS

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the world trend of integrated circuits (ICs) development is urging the reduction of their supply voltage V_{DD} and at the same time the increase of computing power, it is necessary to take these consequences into account, especially in low-voltage analog ICs (AICs). By reducing the circuit elements, the rate of production parameters fluctuation increases, which is caused by fabrication process imperfections. For this reason, it is necessary to take an adequate stand in the design of AICs in order to constantly increase their robustness not only against the fluctuation of technological parameters but also against the V_{DD} temperature variations. These Process-Voltage-Temperature (PVT) variations can be suppressed in various ways, one of which is AICs calibration. As part of the research at our department, a digitally calibrated FDDA was designed, where the overall principle of calibration hardware, its possible influence on the FDDA performance, and a comprehensive overview of simulated and measured results are presented in our work [1]. For better understanding, especially of the mentioned post-calibration configurations, it is advisable to familiarize a reader with this work. As mentioned, the compensated parameter is the input offset voltage V_{IN_OFF} . In our case, the calibration process for V_{IN_OFF} compensation was performed one-time, before the specific FDDA application. This work presents an overview of the simulation configurations that were used in the aforementioned work.

Since FDDA is a specific type of operational amplifier (OPAMP), some configurations presented in the next part of this work (universal) can be used for any FDDA circuit, in order to verify the given parameters. However, it is important to have identical markings of inputs and outputs. This marking is specified in section II. Section III deals with the universal configurations for simulation frequency responses, V_{IN_OFF} , CMRR and PSRR parameters. It includes the effect of small-signal resistance on the FDDA circuit from a low-voltage design point of view. Section IV presents dynamic post-calibration configurations for simulations of the same parameters. In Section V, the relationship among the simulation results obtained by initiated configurations is presented.

II. BACKGROUND

OPAMP is with no doubt one of the most used building blocks in many on-chip AIC applications. In addition to a wide range of uses, there are many application-specific topologies of OPAMPs. However, in the scientific literature, there is diversity in the symbols and designations of individual pins. Thus, it might be useful to establish uniformity in the labeling of individual inputs and outputs of the selected OPAMPs. The first mentioned OPAMP in this paper is fully differential amplifier (FDA), which has a differential output (compared to the standard single-ended topology). Symbol of FDA is presented in Fig. 1 [2], [3], [4], [5].

Fig. 1: FDA symbol.

Individual inputs and outputs are subject to a sign convention that characterizes a 180° phase shift of a specific component of the input differential signal with respect to a specific component of the output differential signal. Fig. 2 shows a trivial FDA topology consisting of an input NMOS differential pair (M_{N1} and M_{N2}) and current source (M_{N3}) and PMOS active loads (M_{P1} and M_{P2}).

Fig. 2: Trivial FDA topology.

The following applies to the individual components of the FDA differential output:

$$V_{OUT+} = A_V(V_{IN+} - V_{IN-}), \quad (1)$$

$$V_{OUT-} = A_V(V_{IN-} - V_{IN+}), \quad (2)$$

where A_V is voltage gain. Based on equations 1 and 2, the FDA differential output voltage is equal to:

$$V_{OUT} = V_{OUT+} - V_{OUT-}, \quad (3)$$

$$V_{OUT} = 2.A_V(V_{IN+} - V_{IN-}). \quad (4)$$

In terms of the FDA function principle and the above equations, it is obvious that it makes no sense to talk about its inverting and non-inverting input-output configuration. When both feedback loops (upper and lower) are implemented, there is always a 180° phase shift between the specific output and input components of the differential signal. Both of these feedback paths will therefore be inverting [6].

The second mentioned type is FDDA. Its symbol is shown in Fig. 3, and the trivial circuit topology in Fig. 4, from which it follows that the FDDA circuit basically consists of two FDAs connected in parallel. Numerical indices of individual inputs indicate a specific differential pair. The sign convention also applies this time, similarly to the FDA. The output marked as V_{OUT+} has a 0° phase shift with respect to the inputs V_{IN1+} and V_{IN2+} , on the contrary with respect to the inputs V_{IN1-} and V_{IN2-} 180° phase shift. An analogous (but opposite in sign) phase dependence applies to output V_{OUT-} [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13].

Fig. 3: FDDA symbol.

Fig. 4: Trivial FDDA topology.

For individual outputs of the FDDA circuit V_{OUT+} and V_{OUT-} apply:

$$V_{OUT+} = A_V[(V_{IN1+} + V_{IN2+}) - (V_{IN1-} + V_{IN2-})], \quad (5)$$

$$V_{OUT-} = A_V[(V_{IN1-} + V_{IN2-}) - (V_{IN1+} + V_{IN2+})], \quad (6)$$

Considering the primary function of the FDDA circuit, using the designation in Fig. 4, for the differential output voltage V_{OUT} applies:

$$V_{OUT} = V_{OUT+} - V_{OUT-}, \quad (7)$$

$$V_{OUT} = 2.A_V[(V_{IN1+} - V_{IN1-}) - (V_{IN2-} - V_{IN2+})]. \quad (8)$$

III. FDDA CONFIGURATIONS

A. Open & closed loop configurations

Elementary configurations of the FDDA circuit, which are in principle the base for all specific simulation connections, are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. In case of Fig. 5, it is a configuration with an open feedback loop. The useful signal is supplied to all four inputs. By this configuration using the equation 8, the self gain of FDDA A_{OL} and corresponding frequency responses can be verified.

Fig. 5: Open loop configuration.

In case of Fig. 6, it is the connection of an FDDA circuit with a closed feedback loop, where the gain of such a configuration is set through the values of resistors R and nR , which is marked as A_{CL} . By means of the mentioned configuration, CL frequency characteristics of the circuit - magnitude and phase, can be simulated. The gain A_{CL} is set as follows:

$$A_{CL} = 1 + \frac{nR}{R} = 1 + n. \quad (9)$$

Fig. 6: Closed loop configuration.

Small-signal output resistance

At this point, it should be noted that the value A_{CL} set by the resistors within the CL configuration is not usually achieved mainly due to the influence of the contribution of the FDDA small-signal output resistance r_{OUT} . The resistance r_{OUT} is increased as a consequence of the low output current. The influence of r_{OUT} on A_{CL} can be expressed through the 2-stage FDDA circuit model in the CL configuration, shown in Fig. 7. Within the model, the input stage is replaced by a Norton current source and the output stage by a Thevenin voltage source. The feedback resistors are labeled R_1 and R_2 . A_{CL} based on the FDDA circuit model equals to:

$$A_{CL} = \frac{G_1 r_{OUT_1st} A_2 (R_1 + R_2)}{R_1 + R_2 + r_{OUT} + G_1 r_{OUT_1st} A_2 R_1}, \quad (10)$$

where G_1 and r_{OUT_1st} are the transconductance and small-signal output resistance of the input stage and A_2 is the gain of the output stage of the FDDA circuit. For the product of quantities $G_1 r_{OUT_1st} A_2$ also applies:

$$G_1 r_{OUT_1st} A_2 = A_{OL}. \quad (11)$$

Fig. 7: Model of 2-stage FDDA circuit.

It follows from the equations 10 and 11:

$$A_{CL} = \frac{(R_1 + R_2)}{\frac{R_1}{A_{OL}} + \frac{R_2}{A_{OL}} + \frac{r_{OUT}}{A_{OL}} + R_1}. \quad (12)$$

With sufficiently low values of R_1 , R_2 and r_{OUT} and at the same time a sufficiently high value of gain A_{OL} , based on the equation 12, it would be possible to achieve the known conventional relation $A_{CL} = 1 + R_2/R_1$. However, as it was mentioned, under the given design conditions, it is necessary to take into account the influence the small-signal output resistance r_{OUT} .

B. V_{IN_OFF} configuration

The configuration of the FDDA circuit for detecting V_{IN_OFF} is a modification of the circuit in CL and it is shown in Fig. 8. This configuration is based on the well-known relation valid for a FDA:

$$V_{IN_OFF} = \frac{V_{OUT} - A_{CL} V_{IN}}{A_{CL}}, \quad (13)$$

where V_{IN} is the input and V_{OUT} is the output differential voltage of the FDDA.

Fig. 8: FDDA offset detection configuration.

In the case of FDDA, connecting the inputs V_{IN1-} and V_{IN2+} to the voltage V_{IN_COMM} (common DC voltage, de facto ground for non-symmetrical V_{DD}) will achieve $V_{IN} = 0$ V, as a result of which only the output offset voltage will be present at the V_{OUT} , so $V_{OUT} = V_{OUT_OFF}$. On the basis of the equation 13 and the stated conditions, the following applies:

$$V_{IN_OFF} = \frac{V_{OUT_OFF}}{A_{CL}}. \quad (14)$$

C. CMRR configuration

In the case of simulation CMRR parameter, the FDDA circuit configuration is used in connection as a voltage follower, which is a special case of CL configuration. This configuration is shown in Fig. 9. The common component of the AC signal is fed to the inputs V_{IN1-} and V_{IN2+} .

Fig. 9: Configuration for CMRR simulation.

For the CMRR, the relationship generally applies:

$$CMRR = \left| \frac{A_{V_DM}}{A_{V_CM}} \right|, \quad (15)$$

where A_{V_DM} and A_{V_CM} are the gains of the differential and common component of the input signal OZ. In the case of the FDDA circuit, it is advantageous to use the connection for the voltage follower due to fixing the differential gain A_{V_DM} to the value of 1 times, or 0 dB, which results in an increase in the efficiency of simulations of this parameter, as it does not have to be simulated in two runs (separately for both gains). In the case of such a connection, the following applies to the CMRR parameter:

$$CMRR = \left| \frac{1}{A_{V_CM}} \right|. \quad (16)$$

D. PSRR configuration

Similar to the simulation of the CMRR parameter, the connection for the voltage follower is also used in this case. The configuration for the simulation of the PSRR parameter for the FDDA circuit is shown in Fig. 10. In this case, only the common DC component of the signal is applied to the V_{IN1-} and V_{IN2+} inputs. The AC component is represented by the source at the supply voltage V_{DD_AC} .

Fig. 10: Configuration for PSRR simulation.

For the PSRR, the equation generally applies:

$$PSRR = \left| \frac{A_{V_DM}}{A_{V_VDD_AC}} \right|, \quad (17)$$

where $A_{V_VDD_AC}$ is the gain of the AC component from the supply voltage. For the same reasons as for the CMRR parameter, also in this case it is appropriate to use the FDDA circuit as a voltage follower. Then, for the PSRR parameter:

$$PSRR = \left| \frac{1}{A_{V_VDD_AC}} \right|. \quad (18)$$

IV. POST-CALIBRATION CONFIGURATIONS

A. Calibration cycle

During the calibration cycle, the FDDA circuit is in OL configuration, with all its inputs connected to the voltage V_{IN_COMM} as shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11: FDDA during calibration cycle.

In terms of the principle of operation of the calibration sub-circuit described in the work [1], it was necessary to implement all post-calibration simulations of individual parameters in time dependence of the duration of the overall calibration cycle. For this reason, following configurations are dynamic, i.e. after a sufficiently long moment of time, the individual connections are switched from the configuration in Fig. 11 to configuration for simulation desired parameter after calibration. For example, in our digital calibration research, the control frequency of calibration cycle was set to 1 kHz. This means that the longest possible time of the total calibration cycle depends on the resolution of the D/A converters. With a 10-bit D/A converter, at a given frequency, 1024 ms would be needed to fully

deplete its range, with a 7-bit 128 ms. It follows that the longest possible (critical) time of the calibration cycle is 1152 ms.

B. Frequency response configuration

In Fig. 12, the dynamic configuration of the FDDA circuit, through which its frequency characteristics after calibration were simulated, is shown. In this state, the FDDA circuit is configured for the calibration cycle itself. After the critical calibration time, the calibrated FDDA circuit was switched to the CL configuration by the ideal switches S_{CL} and $S_{OL/CL}$, followed by the start of the AC analysis.

Fig. 12: Dynamic configuration of the FDDA circuit to simulate its frequency responses after calibration.

C. CMRR & PSRR configurations

On a very similar principle, the parameters CMRR and PSRR were also simulated after calibration, whose dynamic configurations are shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14. After the critical time, the ideal switches S_{OL} , S_{CL} , $S_{OL/CL}$, and in the case of PSRR also the switch S_{VDD} changed their positions, thereby changing the calibration configuration of the FDDA circuit to the desired.

Fig. 13: Dynamic configuration of the FDDA circuit for simulating CMRR parameter.

Fig. 14: Dynamic configuration of the FDDA circuit for simulating PSRR parameter.

V. VERIFICATION OF CONFIGURATIONS

In order to prove the function of the mentioned configurations, 3 types of simulations were selected, where it is possible to observe their interrelationship. Specifically, these are simulations which represent the worst case (WC) of the given parameters at a temperature of 27° within Monte Carlo (MC) analysis. Fig. 15 shows selected magnitude (MFR) and phase (PFR) responses simulated after FDDA calibration. This characteristics were simulated through configuration from Fig. 12. After calibration is finished, the FDDA gain $A_{CL} = 41.55$ dB was achieved, which is about 119.54 times.

Fig. 15: Selected frequency responses of FDDA after calibration.

In Fig. 16, time dependence of the calibration cycle is shown, i.e. zeroing the output offset voltage V_{OUT_OFF} . From this figure it is possible to calculate the value $V_{OUT_OFF} = -1.8541$ mV. By means of A_{CL} and using equation 14 it is possible to calculate the value $V_{IN_OFF} = -15.51$ μ V.

Fig. 16: Selected V_{OUT_OFF} zeroing during the FDDA calibration.

In Fig. 17, a histogram of the input voltage offset is shown. The stated value $V_{IN_OFF} = -15.51$ μ V can be observed in the left part of this graph within a single interval.

Fig. 17: Selected V_{IN_OFF} histogram after FDDA calibration.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents configurations for simulating selected parameters of an unconventional FDDA operational amplifier. All schemes are based on elementary OL or CL connection. Especially for the low-voltage design, the influence of the small-signal output resistance on the gain A_{CL} is also presented. Within these configurations, it is possible to simulate frequency characteristics, input offset voltage V_{IN_OFF} , CMRR and PSRR parameters. Although the above configurations were used for the purpose of FDDA verification within the framework of digital calibration, in general it is certainly possible to apply those categorized as universal. This review can help students of electronics involved in the design of low-voltage AICs to gain their knowledge just by familiarizing themselves with the mentioned schemes and realizing their principle of operation.

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